

Determination of crack bridging laws in tufted composites

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SUMMARY

Mode I and mixed I/II mode crack bridging laws were determined experimentally for single tufts inserted into dry preforms (UD, woven and NCF), infused and cured by RTM process. Glass and carbon threads were tested. Existing analytical models were compared against the results obtained and tuft failure mechanisms identified for different material-loading combinations.

Keywords: Bridging law, traction, pull-out, tufting, RTM

INTRODUCTION

Several structural 3D reinforcement techniques have been developed in order to improve the delamination toughness of polymer composites. These include 3D weaving, stitching and Z-pinning. All aim to improve the interlaminar failure resistance of critical composite structures with minimal reduction in the in-plane properties [1].

Modern one-side stitching, as currently used on the Airbus A380 to join stiffeners to the rear pressure bulkhead, only allows angled insertion of Z-reinforcing threads which reduces the mode I delamination bridging effectiveness. Hence, tufting as modified one-side stitching process has been developed, which enables truly vertical, unstrained insertion of Z-reinforcing threads into dry laminate preforms [2]. This paper reports on a detailed experimental determination of the bridging forces exerted on growing delaminations in simple one-tuft coupons in a variety of reinforcement substrates, in order to determine the sensitivity of the results on the geometry of the reinforcement. The analytical bridging model developed by Cox et al [3,4] is validated against the experimental test results with a critical view on the required model parameters.

LITERATURE

Significant previous work has been carried out on bridging behaviours under mode I loading, for stitched and Z-pinned composites [5-9], whilst only Turrettini [5] and Cartié et al. [6,7] investigated the failure mechanisms of stitches and Z-pins in mode II delamination. Rugg et al. [9] identified the following failure mechanisms which apply to interconnected and independent Z-reinforcement under mode I and II loadings: - initial debonding from surrounding laminate; - elastic stretching of the Z-reinforcement opposed by interface shear friction between laminate and Z-reinforcement; - post debond frictional pull-out for Z-pins, elastic failure of stitches at interface.

Cartié et al. [7] observed the following failure micromechanisms for mode II bridging of carbon Z-pins in unidirectional and woven laminates: - axial shear deformation of the rod with internal matrix cracking; - extensive lateral ploughing through the surrounding resin rich pockets in the laminate.

Several, mainly analytical, models exist to predict Z-reinforcement bridging behaviour. Jain and Mai [11,12] developed a simple mode I and II traction law for stitching based on stitch debonding and elastic stretching. For mode II delamination the stitch model treats the stitch as a rope stretching elastically while neglecting matrix deformation. However, important mechanisms as lateral matrix ploughing and increased interface friction in the zone of deflection are neglected, resulting in oversimplified traction laws, especially for mode II loading. Cox et al. [3,4] developed more complex models for mode I and II crack bridging of stitches and Z-pins. The constitutive models and traction laws are based on the observed failure mechanisms introduced by Rugg et al and extended to cope with snubbing effects reported by Cartié et al. [6,7]. Main challenge of these bridging laws is the experimental determination of the required critical model parameters.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Sample preparation

Figure 1 shows the tufting process used in the present work which is based on a system of commercial tufting head (KSL KL 150) mounted to a Kawasaki 6-axis robot arm (FS20N). The automated tufting system ensures high tufting performance (500 tufts/min) and required insertion positional accuracy.

Figure 1 – Tufting process: (a) carbon thread loops in NCF, (b) tufting schematic, (c) automated tufting head KSL KL150

The fabrics used as substrates were: - carbon 2x2 twill woven 12k OCV fabric (650 g/m^2), non-crimp $0^\circ/90^\circ$ 24k Sigmatex fabric (1010 g/m^2) and unidirectional 6k Hexcel fabric (290 g/m^2). Square panels of $200 \times 180 \text{ mm}^2$ were prepared for each substrate, containing 24 glass and 24 carbon isolated single tufts. The single tufts had a typical free loop length of 3 to 5 mm. An artificial crack was created by placing a release film (thickness 0.03 mm) in the centre plane of the dry laminate preforms. Each panel was injected with aerospace grade RTM epoxy resin ACG MVR 444 – cured for 90 min at 160°C , followed by freestanding post-cure for 120 min at 180°C . The panel thickness of 4.0 mm ensured a comparable fibre volume fraction for all laminates of 55.4 % (twill), 57.4 % (NCF) and 57.0 % (UD).

Square laminate blocks (20 x 20 mm², thickness 4.0 mm) containing a single tuft and an artificial crack were cut with a diamond saw for tuft pull-out and shear specimens.

Table 1 – Properties of commercial tufting threads used

	Glass fibre thread	Carbon fibre threads	
Material	EC 9 68 x 3 S260 T8G Saint Gobain Vetrotex	Tenax® carbon sewing thread	Schappe carbon stretch broken filament thread
Linear weight	204 g/km	137 g/km	80 g/km
Filament count	3x411	2x1000	2x590
Filament diameter	9 mm	7 mm	7mm
Tensile stiffness (impreg.)	42.5 GPa	144.8 GPa	
Tensile strength (impreg.)	1440 MPa	2320 MPa	

Commercially available Saint Gobain glass and Tenax carbon sewing yarns had been selected as tufting threads. Both threads have comparable cross-sections and are highly twisted to facilitate the tuft insertion and to minimize the thread breakage (see table 1). Schappe stretch broken carbon thread was added to compare the influence of tuft thread size. Tensile tests on manufactured thread rodstock determined tensile strength of 1440 / 2320 MPa and tensile stiffness of 42.5 / 144.8 GPa for impregnated glass and carbon threads respectively. Straightness of the tufts in the cured laminate was ensured by sufficient consolidation of the laminate preforms during the tuft insertion process and confirmed by micrographs showing tuft deviation only near the laminate surface.

Mode I pull-out test

Single tuft specimens were tested in mode I pull-out configuration to determine the traction-displacement relation, also known as the bridging law of single tufts. Each sample was bonded with cyanoacrylate between two vertically loaded steel t-tabs which were sprayed with a black and white paint speckle pattern. Two opposing cameras, placed equidistant in front and back of the sample, recorded a sequence of images of the moving speckle pattern. The displacement of the random pattern in these images was analysed by a Limes 2D digital image correlation system (DIC) to determine the relative pull-out and possible shear displacement of each specimen corner (see figure 2.a and b).

Figure 2 – Pull-out setup: (a) pull-out schematic, (b) pull-out test setup with DIC equipment, (c) specimen between metal tabs with speckle pattern, (d) twill and NCF single tuft specimens with glass tuft

At least ten specimens were tested for each tuft and laminate material combination. The samples were loaded at a constant cross-head speed of 0.25 mm/min in a universal test machine Instron 5500 R with 5kN load cell. Typical crack bridging laws were recorded until tuft failure, consisting of pull-out load and total crack opening displacement Δv . Post-mortem analysis based on SEM and micrographs was performed to identify the failure mechanisms of the tested single tufts. The dissipated bridging energy during pull-out was calculated, based on the numerical integration of the area under the load-displacement curves for elastic stretching and pull-out of the broken tuft.

In order to distinguish between the determined energy dissipation mechanisms during the debonding and the failure of a single tuft, additional pull-out tests were performed on modified single tuft-laminate specimens in which a 0.5 mm thick resin-rich outer layer containing the tuft loop had been ground off. This avoided the tuft loops on the laminate surface inhibiting the frictional pull-out of the debonded tuft into the bridged delamination crack. These tests were carried out for six NCF laminate specimens with Tenax carbon thread tufts, at cross-head speed of 1mm/min.

Mixed mode shear test

Previous work in the group [7] showed that pure mode II loading of Z-reinforced laminates cannot be applied in practice, due to opening mechanisms acting in the delamination crack. Uneven crack surfaces and deformed Z-reinforcement components under shear displacement force the delamination crack apart, thus creating mixed mode loading conditions. A modified shear jig was developed in this study, which allows the crack to open in order to overcome locking mechanisms of the uneven crack surfaces.

Figure 3 – Mixed mode shear test setup: (a) shear schematic, (b) shear test jig with applied speckle pattern, (c) cracked resin rich pocket around single tuft in NCF

Crack opening is enabled in the modified shear jig by pivoting the opposing shear arms (figure 3.a). A Limes 3D digital image correlation system with stereo camera systems recorded the relative opening Δu and shear Δv displacement components of the opposing shear arms by measuring changes in the applied speckle pattern on the jig surface (see figure 3.b).

At least ten specimens for each tuft-laminate material combination were tested under mixed mode shear displacement. Each specimen was bonded between the two shear arms and subsequently loaded parallel to the delamination crack with constant cross-head speed of 0.25 mm/min. The top shear jig arm was attached to a 5kN load cell which recorded the bridging traction of the single tuft specimens.

Whenever a tuft is inserted into NCF or UD laminate, a typical resin rich pocket is created around the tuft which stretches along the laminate fibre direction, as displayed in figure 3.c. To determine the influence of the surrounding laminate geometry on the shear behaviour, single tufts in NCF and UD laminates were tested in two directions, parallel (0°) and orthogonal (90°) to the fibre direction at the crack surface.

Results

Figure 4 shows representative pull-out load-displacement curves for different tuft-laminate material combinations. Initially, the intact tuft and surrounding laminate stretch elastically. At a load of about 70 N the tuft starts to debond from the surrounding laminate resulting in a non-linear decrease in the slope. Debonding cracks start at the crack interface and propagate along the tuft towards the laminate surface (see figure 5.c). As soon as the internal axial stress in the tuft reaches the material strength, the tuft fails abruptly at the point of maximum stress concentration. In some cases the individual thread or yarn components of the tuft fail separately due to different local alignment. Remaining thread components are pulled out under friction.

Figure 4 – Experimental pull-out bridging laws for different material combinations

Figure 4.a suggests the existence of almost identical pull-out laws for NCF and twill woven fabric, which is supported by equivalent energy dissipation values in table 2. Single tufts in unidirectional fabric were able to carry higher maximum bridging loads but reached lower crack opening before failure.

The comparison of different tuft thread materials reveals a reduction of 40% in energy dissipation with reduced bridging load for glass thread tufts, thought to be due to the lower stiffness and tuft circumference of the glass thread. The change from Tenax thread to stretch broken carbon thread with reduced diameter caused the carbon tuft to fail at lower loads, at lower crack opening displacement.

Resin rich pockets in twill woven and non-crimp fabrics are larger than required to accommodate the single tufts, due to locking effects between the different laminate layers (figure 3.c). Most resin rich pockets in both materials contained pre-cracks, probably due to high residual curing stresses between the local resin rich region and the surrounding laminate. Both factors allow the single tuft to stretch and align resulting in

increased pull-out length compared to the elastic deformation limit of a perfectly straight thread rodstock.

Table 2 – Pull-out load and energy for various laminate-tuft combinations

Specimen	Max. load [N] (Stdev.)	Pull-out energy [Nmm] (Stdev.)	Specimen	Max. load [N] (Stdev.)	Pull-out energy [Nmm] (Stdev.)
Twill C-tuft	231 (45)	55 (20)	Twill G-tuft	165 (32)	35 (10)
NCF C-tuft	231 (29)	55 (15)	NCF G-tuft	162 (17)	32 (8)
NCF C-stretch	168 (34)	24 (6)			
UD C-tuft	266 (28)	41 (11)	UD G-tuft	184 (23)	25 (5)

In the unidirectional fabric the width of resin rich pockets is smaller. Tuft yarns appear to spread along the resin rich pocket thus increasing the frictional surface area. The analysis of pull-out tuft failure shows that almost all single tuft specimens failed at the crack interface, for both glass and carbon threads. Hence, frictional pull-out of broken yarn segments (as shown in figure 5.a) contributes only little additional energy dissipation.

Figure 5 – Pull-out micrographs: (a) pulled out thread section, (b) thread failure at crack interface, (c) debonded tuft prior to failure

The response of the tuft-laminate combinations changes significantly if mixed mode loading is applied. Figure 6 displays the mixed mode bridging laws, separated into shear and opening displacement curves for the different material combinations. After the initial elastic deformation of the tuft, subsequent crack surface displacement is highly dependent on the nature of the surrounding laminate. If a single tuft in unidirectional and non-crimp fabric is loaded parallel to the fibre direction at crack interface of the laminate the tuft debonds from the surrounding laminate and ploughs into the resin rich area of its resin pocket. The maximum bridging load is reduced but can be maintained for very large shear displacement until the maximum strength of the tuft is reached. Crack opening for parallel loaded specimens is small compared to the total shear displacement. If the tuft is loaded orthogonal to the main fibre direction, its shear displacement is highly constrained by the adjacent fibre laminate. Higher bridging loads

can be achieved. However, the total dissipated energy is reduced due to reduced total crack sliding displacement.

Figure 6 – Experimental bridging laws for carbon tufted laminates, loaded with (0°) and against (90°) the laminate direction at crack interface: (left) crack shear component, (right) crack opening component

The complexity of weave pattern in twill woven specimens causes a mixed reply of the single tuft under shear loading. Depending on the position of the tuft in the weave pattern resin ploughing or fibre locking prevail, leading to increase of scatter in the measured energy values.

Table 3 – Shear load and energy for single carbon tufts in various laminates

Specimen		Max. load [N] (Stdev.)	Shear energy [Nmm] (Stdev.)		
			U-component	V-component	Total
Twill C-tuft		270 (87)	74 (21)	37 (14)	88 (27)
NCF C-tuft	0°	180 (34)	69 (14)	17 (5)	78 (16)
	90°	241 (82)	55 (16)	14 (7)	61 (18)
UD C-tuft	0°	179 (22)	59 (17)	17 (5)	68 (20)
	90°	520 (112)	89 (20)	66 (21)	118 (27)

Figure 7 displays SEM images of 0° and 90° loaded NCF specimens. In general, the zone of resin ploughing is limited to the resin rich area near the crack surface causing the tuft to shear in a typical ‘S’-shape, accompanied by extensive internal splitting and debonding of the tuft yarns (figure 7.c).

Orthogonal loading (90°) leads to higher mode I/II shear ratios in all laminate types. Deformed and debonded tuft sections are forced onto the crack surface instead of into the surrounding laminate. The high load values for 90° sheared unidirectional specimens are a combination of tuft bridging with increased interfacial friction and locking effects of the uneven crack surface. The axial stress in the tuft reaches its maximum at the crack surface which causes most tufts in mixed mode shear to fail at the crack surface.

Figure 8 presents the comparison of pull-out bridging laws for modified NCF and intact tuft specimens. The shaded area indicates the energy which was dissipated during pull-out of the tuft with removed thread loop. Frictional pull-out of modified NCF specimens increases the dissipated energy by 83% to 100Nmm for a pull-out length of 2.2 mm. If a

constant, uniform shear friction is assumed along the length of the debonded tuft, the energy value can be used to calculate the equivalent shear friction τ . For NCF laminate a constant shear friction of 37 (+/-6) MPa was measured for the modified single tuft specimens.

Figure 7 – Shear micrographs: (a) 90° loading to interface fibre direction, (b) 0° loading to interface fibre direction, (c) debonded tuft before failure

Figure 8 – Comparison of pull-out bridging laws for carbon tufts in NCF with and without tuft loop

ANALYTICAL MODEL

The analytical bridging model of Cox et al [3,4, 13] for mode I and mixed mode crack bridging of continuous and discontinuous Z-reinforcements neglects the initial elastic deformation of laminate; stitches are assumed to debond and stretch under axial loading σ , surface thread elements are pulled into the laminate surface under increased axial load, axial sliding of the stitch is opposed by uniform interfacial shear traction τ , the

stitch deforms internally in shear as rigid/ perfectly plastic material, and the stitch ploughs laterally through the surrounding laminate in mode II loading which is opposed by hydrostatic pressure σ_h of the rigid/perfectly plastic laminate.

The failure micromechanisms observed in this work confirm the existence of axial debonding, stretching and resin ploughing. Only debonding and lateral crushing of the surface thread into the laminate could not be observed. Hence, the analytical model for interconnected Z-reinforcements in laminates with finite thickness was applied to predict the experimentally determined single tuft bridging laws.

The model relies on the experimental determination of the following geometrical and mechanical parameters: circumference s and cross-section A of tuft and surface thread (indicated by asterisk), laminate half thickness h , elastic stiffness of the tufting thread E_t , shear friction τ , friction enhancement factor μ , and hydrostatic pressure of laminate around tuft σ_h and on laminate surface σ_h^* .

The geometrical parameters, as well as the tuft stiffness and interfacial shear traction can be determined experimentally, as presented above. However, friction enhancement factor and crush strength as critical factors for the mixed mode model solution are difficult to measure. With a determined shear traction of 37 MPa and an assumed typical hydraulic pressure σ_h^* of 900 MPa, taken from literature [13], the initial analytical curves for NCF always overestimated the slope of the bridging law. Change in the hydraulic pressure of the laminate surface did not achieve better results. This discrepancy can be partially explained by the model assumption of a perfectly straight Z-reinforcement. Tufts, even if normal to the laminate plane, consist of highly twisted yarns which separate under pull-out load and increase the pull-out length.

Figure 10 – Comparison of analytical bridging laws with experiment for mode I pull-out of C-tufts in NCF

Only the reduction of applied shear traction to 6.5 MPa lead to accurate predictions for mode I single tuft pull-out of NCF laminate (see figure 10). If then combined with an assumed hydraulic pressure of 42 MPa and 104 MPa for loading parallel and orthogonal to the laminate fibre direction, mixed mode bridging for NCF specimens could be simulated accurately. However, an ultimate failure criterion is missing in the analytical model to predict the total strength σ_m of single tufts.

CONCLUSIONS

The single tuft response under mode I pull-out load depends mainly on tuft stiffness and the resin stress state. The surrounding fabric type has only small effect on the pull-out response. Energy dissipation is dominated by debonding and frictional stretching until ultimate failure of the tuft at the crack surface. In contrast, single tuft bridging laws for mixed mode shearing depend highly on the mechanical and geometrical properties of the surrounding laminate. If loaded parallel to the laminate fibre direction, the tuft ploughs through its surrounding resin rich pocket followed by reduced bridging loads, but large crack shear displacement and corresponding high energy dissipation. If sheared 90° to the fabric, the surrounding laminate withstands the tuft causing the tuft to pull into the crack surface and to increase the mode I/II crack opening ratio.

The given analytical model showed to be capable predicting the failure mechanisms of bridging tufts for different loading ratios, provided that the critical model parameters such as shear friction and crushing strength are adjusted, specific to each reinforcement geometry. The reasons for the discrepancies require further study. Test of application of the single tuft bridging laws in finite element models for mode I and mixed mode delamination propagation in DCB specimens is underway in the authors' laboratory.

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